

Determinants of Household Out-Migration in Selected Blocks of Nawada District, Bihar

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Abstract

The present study is primarily focused on the influencing factors that decide out-migration from selected blocks (Nawada and Rajauli) in the district. With the help of primary data collected through 200 households during 2023-24, an analysis applies the Chi-square test and binary logistic regression model in order to get a better understanding of how socio-economic characteristics, employment security, and welfare access influence the migration decision. The findings from the blocks reveal certain regional similarities in out-migration patterns, but there are clear differences in landownership and educational attainment. Further, the bivariate analysis shows a significant association between landownership, employment security, and migration, but gender and public distribution system (PDS) access are not significant. Multivariate results reveal that agricultural land ownership is the strongest determinant of out-migration in the district. The households who owned lands had less chance to migrate outside, especially in Nawada, which suggests spatial variation. Job security and welfare access fail to maintain independent statistical significance. Overall, the findings emphasize the importance of productive assets in influencing migration decisions.

Keywords

Household Out-Migration; Agricultural Land; Spatial Heterogeneity; Welfare Access; PDS.

Introduction

Migration in India has emerged as a major socio-economic process influencing multiple dimensions of household life. It reshapes livelihood strategies, labor market structures, and demographic trends. Internal migration, particularly rural-to-urban flows, reveals persistent stagnation in agricultural practices and increasing reliance on urban-based industries. According to National Statistical Office (2022), nearly 29 percent of India's population can be classified as migrants, with rural households accounting for a higher share of migration participation. Multiple determinants, including landholding size, income diversification, caste status, educational attainment, and access to welfare programs, play a significant role in shaping migration patterns (Kumari & Pandey, 2024). Migration is not merely a demographic process, but it is a livelihood strategy that is shaped by poverty, limited local employment opportunities, and agrarian vulnerability, enabling households to diversify income and reallocate labor (Kusumo et al., 2023). Therefore, to understand migration in a well-structured manner, a household perspective is very essential, as household decisions are embedded in socio-economic realities, resource constraints, and welfare access. In India, Bihar occupies an important place in migration discussions. People often view Bihar as a remittance economy due to the significant number of individuals who have relocated outside the state for employment over an extended period.

Several Indian states face high rates of out-migration, with rural households migrating seasonally or long-term due to livelihood insecurity, few local jobs, and agrarian distress (Srivastava, 2020; Kesar et al., 2021). There are multiple drivers of migration, such as poverty, unemployment, small and fragmented landholdings, caste-based inequalities, and limited industrialization (Kumari & Pandey, 2024). Kumar and Hashia (2018) further highlighted that the pattern of migration in Bihar has undergone significant transformation over time, with growing reliance on employment-oriented migration towards urban centers of other states, mostly concentrated in non-agricultural sectors such as construction, transport, and informal services.

Objective of study

A deep socio-economic disparity is seen among Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Other Backward Classes (OBCs) because of a higher rate of out-migration within these categories (Kumar, 2024). The remittance sent back home by the migrants helps in uplifting their families' social status and eradicating the poverty to some extent, but they do create a dependency and expose families to vulnerabilities associated with insecure employment and lack of social protection (Muragod &

Patil, 2024). Therefore, the migration from Bihar does not depend on a single parameter, but it is a story of both resilience and vulnerability, shaped by structural constraints and household-level determinants. Within Bihar, the Nawada district reflects challenges of out-migration at the local level. Situated in South Bihar, this district is known for its heavy reliance on agriculture and underdeveloped industrial growth. As reported by Kumar (2023), the migration pattern of Nawada undergoes significant change due to increasing dependency on the urban informal labor market.

The empirical studies show that the households that have better access to social protection and welfare schemes are less likely to engage in the distress-driven migration (Imbert & Papp, 2022). The recent pandemic, COVID-19, highlighted the unstable situation of migrant families, as the pandemic distorted the employment opportunities and access to welfare, leaving many stranded without income or support (Muragod & Patil, 2024). The access to different welfare in Nawada is not very easy for the household; therefore, they often have to choose between insecure local employment and uncertain migration opportunities.

Although there is several literature available on migration from Bihar, most existing research addresses state-level trends, overlooking household-level determinants that vary across regions (Kumari & Pandey, 2024), but in districts like Nawada, a micro-level study is still needed to understand about those drivers that operate at the household level and play a key decisive factor for the migration of people outside the state. Nawada is known for its unique socio-economic profile characterized by higher dependency on agriculture, caste stratification, and welfare exclusion, necessitating a focused analysis. The present research work is guided by two research objectives: first, to examine the socio-economic characteristics of migrant and non-migrant households in Nawada district, Bihar, and second, to assess the influence of household-level economic assets, employment security, and access to welfare schemes on out-migration from Nawada district, Bihar. Therefore the present study seeks to identify the socio-economic characteristics and household-level determinants that influence migration decisions in the district.

Review of Literature

The study of migration in India has evolved through multiple theoretical and empirical views, which include frameworks on classical push-pull theories to socio-economic analyses of various determinants done at the household level. The push-pull theory, originally given by Ravenstein and later refined by Lee, remains a foundational base to understand that migration is a response against disparities in employment, income, and living conditions. Although the contemporary researchers emphasize that migration is not an individual decision but rather involves a holistic response of families, which is decided by socio-economic assets, welfare access, and structural inequalities (Rajan & Sumeetha, 2020). The current studies are giving more emphasis on the household's perspective to understand migration and the decision to migrate from the origin. Kumari and Pandey (2024) argue that the existing socio-economic condition of the household, landholding size, and disparities in income have a direct influence on migration decisions. Therefore, this proves that the households with limited agricultural assets or insecure employment are more likely to migrate towards urban centers for their earnings.

Bihar is always recognized as one of the most migration-prone states in India. The survey done by the National Statistical Office (NSO, 2021) confirms that the rate of rural out-migration from Bihar is very high, with rural households particularly vulnerable to seasonal and long-term migration. Further, Kumari and Pandey (2024) observe that migration patterns in Bihar have shifted and become increasingly concentrated in non-agricultural activities, particularly construction and informal services located in urban centers, thereby fundamentally transforming labor market dynamics. Remittance sent by the migrant to their families helps in eradicating poverty, but at the same time it creates dependency and exposes the households to vulnerabilities associated with insecure employment and lack of social protection (Muragod & Patil, 2024). At the district level, Nawada shows a complex interlinkage of factors that influences migration at the micro level. Further, Kumar (2023) mentioned that the households in the Nawada district are mostly now relying on the informal sector's jobs and sending members to urban centers who are mostly engaged in the construction and transport sectors. Access to welfare schemes in the district plays a very crucial role in deciding the migration of household members from their origin. Kumari (2025) highlights that exclusion from access to MGNREGA and other PDS schemes puts pressure on the individuals; as a result, they are forced to migrate. The recent COVID-19 pandemic shows the fragility of migrant households, with mobility restrictions and lockdown measures causing massive job losses and poor access to welfare schemes and social protection (Kesar et.al.,2021).Therefore, these studies show the importance of the integration of welfare access and employment security into household level migration analysis.Despite extensive research work already done in the area of migration from Bihar, a clear gap is still seen when district-level analysis needs attention in this regard. Most of the

works on migration in Bihar are primarily focused on a broader concept like the movement of people from origin to destination, and the most common reason for that is jobs. A similar pattern is followed by district-level analysis. Hardly any work is focused on the determinant that exactly puts pressure to move from origin to destination. The present study seeks to address this gap by employing a rigorous and context-specific methodology, as detailed in the subsequent sections.

Methodology

The present study is based on the primary household survey data that was collected during 2023-24 from two blocks district which includes Nawada and Rajauli. This district is characterized by a predominant agrarian region, small land holdings, seasonal agricultural opportunities, and very limited non farm livelihood opportunities, conditions commonly associated with a high level of rural out-migration (Bhagat, 2021). To ensure spatial representation across all the blocks in the district, a multi-stage sampling design was adopted following standard survey methods used in rural population studies (Cochran, 1977). The blocks were selected from different geographical regions in the district, and then random selection of villages was done through stratified random sampling technique.

The sample comprised 200 households. The data were collected from a structured set of questionnaires by conducting face-to-face interviews with households. The pooled logistic model with interaction term is used to analyze the key factors influencing household out-migration and to check whether these factors differ across blocks. The dependent variable is a binary indicator of household out-migration, coded 1 if any household member migrated outside Nawada district for work and 0 otherwise.

The model is specified as:

$$\log\left(\frac{P_i}{1 - P_i}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_i + \beta_2 BLOCK_i + \beta_3 (X_i \times BLOCK_i)$$

Where:

P_i denotes the probability of out-migration for household i ;

X_i represents household-level characteristics including agricultural land ownership, employment security, educational attainment, gender, and access to the Public Distribution System;

$BLOCK_i$ is a binary indicator distinguishing Rajauli and Nawada blocks;

$X_i \times BLOCK_i$ captures block-specific differences in the effects of key predictors.

The model was estimated using maximum likelihood methods, with model fit assessed using standard diagnostic tests (Hosmer, Lemeshow, & Sturdivant, 2013).

Result and Discussion

Table 1. Socio-economic characteristics of migrant and non-migrant households in Nawada district

Characteristics / Variable	Category	Nawada (%)	Rajauli (%)
Gender	Male	99	94
	Female	1	6
Household out-migration	Yes	37	33
	No	63	67
Educational qualification	Illiterate	2	14
	Below primary	13	27
	Primary	19	32
	Secondary	32	11
	Higher secondary	32	15
	Graduation & above	2	1
Agricultural land ownership	Yes	71	53
	No	29	47

Characteristics / Variable	Category	Nawada (%)	Rajauli (%)
Govt./private job in family	Yes	13	17
	No	87	83
PDS ration access	Yes	87	77
	No	13	23
Age of respondent (years)	Mean	41.6	44.9
Household size (members)	Mean	10.4	9.8

Source: Primary data

Table 1 summarizes the socio-economic characteristics of sampled households that have been obtained from Rajauli and Nawada blocks. Most of the respondents are predominantly male in both the blocks. 99% of males from the Nawada block and 94% of males from the Rajauli block participated in the survey. In Rajauli, the mean age is slightly higher, at 44.9 years, than in Nawada, where it is 41.6 years. Although the average household size is larger in Nawada 10.4 members compared to Rajauli 9.8 members. About one-third of households in both blocks, 37% in Nawada and 33% in Rajauli, accepted migrating outside the state for earnings. This represents an almost similar level of out-migration in both blocks. However, a clear difference is noticed at the level of education. The concentration of higher-secondary and secondary education is larger in Nawada as compared with Rajauli. The economic conditions are different in both the blocks. The land ownership is substantially higher in Nawada 71% compared with Rajauli (53%). Not much representation is seen in the governmental sector job from both blocks, and it is only reported 13% in Nawada and 17% in Rajauli. Therefore, the descriptive statistics shown in Table 1 indicate similar trends in migration across both blocks with a noticeable difference in education, land ownership, and access to welfare schemes. These inter-block contrasts establish the empirical foundation for **the subsequent bivariate and multivariate analyses.**

Table 2 given below indicates a block wise Chi-square test that examines the association between selected household characteristics and out-migration. **Table-2 Block-wise association between household characteristics and out-migration in Nawada district**

Explanatory Variable	Nawada block χ^2 (df)	p-value	Hypothesis decision (Nawada)	Rajauli block χ^2 (df)	p-value	Hypothesis decision (Rajauli)
Gender of household head	0.593 (1)	0.441	Fail to reject H_{01}	0.770 (1)	0.38	Fail to reject H_{01}
Educational qualification	10.455 (5)	0.063	Fail to reject H_{01}	15.078 (5)	0.01	Reject H_{01}
Ownership of agricultural land	42.428 (1)	<0.001	Reject H_{01}	13.087 (1)	<0.001	Reject H_{01}
Employment security (Govt./Private job)	8.776 (1)	0.003	Reject H_{02}	6.812 (1)	0.009	Reject H_{02}
Access to PDS	0.249 (1)	0.618	Fail to reject H_{02}	0.646 (1)	0.422	Fail to reject H_{02}

Source: Primary data

With the help of bivariate analysis, the chi-square test result is obtained. Although both migrant and non-migrant households are dominated by male members as heads of families in both blocks, the Chi-square test result indicates no statistically significant relation between head of the family and out-migration, i.e., either block Nawada ($\chi^2(1) = 0.593$, $p = 0.441$) or Rajauli ($\chi^2(1) = 0.770$, $p = 0.380$). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) cannot be rejected with respect to gender. The analysis of education reveals that it has a differential impact in both blocks. In

Nawada, the Chi-square result ($\chi^2(5)=10.455, p=0.063$) means there is no statistically significant relation between educational attainment and migration status. Conversely, in Rajauli block, a significant relationship is observed ($\chi^2(5)=15.078, p=0.010$) in this same category.

In contrast with the early two findings, a substantial difference was clearly observed between migrant and non-migrant households in land ownership. The Chi-square test confirms a strong association between land ownership and household out migration in Nawada block ($\chi^2(1)=42.428, p<0.001$) and Rajauli ($\chi^2(1)=13.087, p<0.001$). Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected in both blocks, showing the land ownership plays a critical role as a determinant of migration. Further findings reveals that employment security and household migration status in both the blocks has a statistically significant association. This means H_{02} is rejected for employment security in the Nawada and Rajauli blocks, underscoring the role of employment security in influencing household out-migration decisions. In contrast, although most of the household accept to get the benefits of subsidized food through the Public Distribution System (PDS), no statistically significant association is observed between PDS access and migration status in either block. Therefore, with respect to welfare access, H_{02} cannot be rejected. This means that PDS coverage alone does not differentiate significantly between migrant and non-migrant households. Overall, the evidence drawn from bivariate analysis shows ownership and employment security are consistently associated with household out-migration.

Table–3 Logistic Regression estimates of household out-migration with block interactions

Predictor	B	Odds Ratio (Exp(B))	95% CI	p-value
Agricultural land (Yes) – Effect in Rajauli (β_1)	-3.555	0.029	0.007 – 0.115	<0.001
Land × Block (Nawada) (β_3)	-2.715	0.066	0.011 – 0.401	0.003
Agricultural land (Yes) – Effect in Nawada ($\beta_1 + \beta_3$)	-6.27	≈0.002	Derived from combined coefficients	—
Block (Nawada = 1) (β_2)	-29.364	0	Not estimable†	0.999
PDS access (Yes)	0.995	2.705	0.916 – 7.991	0.072
Gender (Male)	0.63	1.877	0.175 – 20.091	0.603

Source - Primary data

[Notes: Odds ratios (Exp(B)) are reported. Nawada block is the reference category for block comparisons. The dependent variable is household out-migration (1 = yes, 0 = no). Confidence intervals are at the 95 per cent level. Model fit was assessed using the Hosmer–Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test.]

A binary logistic model is further used in this study in order to get confirmation about the determinant of household out-migration. The model includes an interaction between land ownership and block location to test for spatial differences. The logistic regression model shows a statistically significant result, which is indicated through the Omnibus test ($\chi^2(14)=94.311, p<0.001$), confirming that the predictors collectively enhance model performance compared to the null model. A moderate explanatory power is seen in Nagelkerke R^2 value of 0.518, while the Hosmer–Lemeshow test ($\chi^2(8)=5.806, p=0.669$) indicates that the model provides a satisfactory fit to the observed data. This model shows solid predictive performance and correctly classifies 82 percent of cases. The findings determine that agricultural land ownership is the only predictive determinant of household out-migration; however, in Rajauli, owning land reduces the chance of migration by nearly 97 percent compared to landless families. Further, the regression result shows a statistically significant interaction effect (B = -2.715, OR = 0.066, p = 0.003) between land ownership and block location. This demonstrates that the effect of land ownership is not uniform across both blocks.

The combined coefficient ($\beta_1 + \beta_3 = -6.270$) for the Nawada block shows an estimated odds ratio of approximately 0.002. This means households with landownership are less prone to out-migration. For combined effects, SPSS does not provide confidence intervals directly; therefore, the conclusions are drawn from the significance of the coefficients. Conclusively, the result in this category shows how landownership reduces the chances of out-migration. Access to PDS (Public Distribution System) exhibits a positive association with out-migration ($B = 0.995$, $OR = 2.705$, $p = 0.072$); however, this positive association does not attain a conventional significance level. Similarly, the gender of the household head ($p = 0.603$), educational qualification (joint test $p = 0.074$), and employment security ($p = 0.998$) do not demonstrate statistically significant independent effects once the interaction structure is incorporated. Therefore, the overall result confirms that agricultural land ownership is one of the key determinants of household out-migration, with a strong positive impact in the Nawada and Rajauli blocks.

6. Discussion

The present study aimed to analyze (i) the socio-economic profiles of migrant and non-migrant households and (ii) the effects of household-level economic assets, employment security, and welfare access on out-migration in selected blocks of Nawada district. Therefore, the results derived provide substantive support to some extent for the stated hypotheses in this study. For Hypothesis 1, the results show that the socio-economic characteristics of households do not uniformly determine the household out-migration. The gender of the household is not showing any statistically significant result in either analysis, meaning migration is not shaped by headship. The attainment of education exhibits block-specific significance in bivariate analysis, and its result is significant in Rajauli but not in Nawada. Therefore, this means that education does not independently determine household out-migration.

With reference to the other socio-economic indicators, the agricultural land ownership emerges as the most stable and influential determinant of household out-migrants, leading to the rejection of H_{01} . The combined results derived from both statistical tests show that households with land ownership are less likely to migrate. Further, the multivariate analysis indicates the spatial heterogeneity, meaning the impact of landownership is substantial in Rajauli block ($OR = 0.029$, $p < 0.001$) and markedly stronger in Nawada block (derived $OR \approx 0.002$). So, this confirms that the assets work differently in different local contexts and supports theories that link migration to asset constraints rather than individual traits. The results for Hypothesis 2 show a layered and context-dependent pattern. Bivariate analysis in both blocks shows statistically significant results for employment security, resulting in the rejection of H_{02} at that level; however, its impact diminishes in the multivariate logistic specification once agricultural land ownership and block level interaction effects are introduced.

The employment coefficient becomes statistically insignificant, indicating potential multicollinearity or shared variance with asset variables. Therefore, the employment security appears to be associated with underlying asset ownership structures rather than functioning as an independent determinant of migration behavior.

Another determinant, like PDS, does not show any statistically significant association in the chi-square test. However, the logistic regression model reveals a marginal positive coefficient ($OR = 2.705$, $p = 0.072$); it fails to attain conventional levels of statistical significance. So for access to welfare schemes, H_{02} cannot be definitively rejected. Therefore, findings reveal PDS alone may be insufficient to reduce migration pressure within structurally constrained rural contexts.

Overall discussion reveals a clear pattern: the ownership of land helps to counter household out-migration, while welfare access and job security have weaker and situation-based effects. Further, this discussion shows that the reasons for migration vary across the blocks within the same districts. Therefore, this study reveals that there is a need for a household-focused and context-aware approach when studying migration in farming regions like Nawada.

Conclusion

The present study shows that household outmigration in the Nawada district is mostly influenced by structural economic factors, and agricultural land ownership emerges as the most decisive determinant. However, the land does not provide the same security everywhere, and its impact is weaker in the Rajauli block. Employment stability, educational attainment, and welfare accessibility are important for household welfare, but they do not eradicate migration pressure autonomously, especially in the areas of limited economic prospects. Therefore, in such a case, the migration becomes a valid decision made by households facing long-term structural difficulties instead of simple proof that development efforts have failed. Therefore, after systematically identifying block-level differences in migration determinants, the present study shows a critical need for careful design and context-based developmental programs that

Suggestions for the future Study

help in checking and minimizing distress-induced mobility and at the same time enhance the resilience and sustainability of rural livelihood systems.

Based on the findings, the following suggestions and policy recommendations are proposed: Block specific livelihood strategies: The land ownership reduces migration in Rajauli, but the magnitude of its protective effect is weaker compared to Nawada, indicating the importance of block specific policy interventions. Promotion and expansion of local non agricultural employment opportunities: The skill development programs must be strategically aligned with the availability of local resources instead of adopting standardized training models. 3. Enhancement of asset based policy interventions Focus must be given to policy interventions that strengthen productive assets such as land development, livestock ownership, and microenterprise promotion, which are expected to give more positive results in comparison to standalone policies. 4. Reconceptualizing the relationship between welfare provisions and migration dynamics Welfare programmes should be structured to complement migration processes by enhancing food security and mitigating household vulnerability. 5. Implementing targeted and need-based support mechanisms for blocks exhibiting high socio-economic vulnerability Focus should be given to both blocks, namely Rajauli and Nawada, to identify the vulnerable categories associated with out-migration and to design targeted development plans that address their structurally weak livelihood base.

References

1. Imbert, C., & Papp, J. (2022). Short-term migration, rural welfare programs, and urban labor markets: Evidence from India. *American Economic Journal: Applied Economics*, 14 (2), 217–252.
2. Kesar, S., Abraham, R., Lahoti, R., Nath, P., & Basole, A. (2021). Pandemic, informality, and vulnerability: Impact of COVID-19 on livelihoods in India. *Canadian Journal of Development Studies/Revue canadienne d'études du développement*, 42(1-2), 145-164. Kumari, J., & Pandey, S. K. (2024). Impact of Bihar's migration on poverty and multidimensional deprivation. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 12(7), 505–507. <https://www.ijcrt.org>
3. Kusumo, R. A. B., Kurnia, G., Setiawan, I., & Tirtosudarmo, R. (2023). Migration and Farmer household livelihood strategies: factors influencing the decision to migrate. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science & Humanities*, 31(1), 57–79. <https://doi.org/10.47836/pjssh.31.1.04>
4. Kumar, A., & Haseena Hashia, Prof. (2018). Trends and Patterns of Out-migration from Bihar. *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 8(11), 490–493. <http://www.ijmra.us>
5. Kumar, A. (2023). A contrastive analysis of the changing migration patterns in the Nawada district.
6. Remarking an Analisation, VIII–E-8-E-15 (VIII November-2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10159598>
7. Kumar, N. (2024). Mapping Migration of Different Social Groups: Learnings from Rural Bihar. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews*, 11(1), 702–704. <https://ijrar.org/papers/IJRAR24A1229.pdf>
8. Kumari, N. (2025). Socio-Economic profile of Bihar: challenges, opportunities, and pathways to sustainable development [Research Journal]. *SHODH SAMAG*, 08–08(03), 1179–1185. <https://www.shodhsamagam.com>
9. Muragod, R. P., & Patil, S. L. (2024). A STUDY ON SOCIAL SECURITY AND WELFARE SCHEMES FOR MIGRANT WORKERS IN INDIA: A GLANCE [Journal-article]. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 12(Issue 3 March 2024), c366–c368. <https://www.ijcrt.org>
10. National Statistical Office [NSO] (2022) Migration in India, 2020–21: Periodic Labour Force Survey (July 2020–June 2021). Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India. <https://www.mospi.gov.in>
11. Rajan, S. I., & Sumeetha, M. (2020). *Handbook of internal migration in India*. SAGE Publications Pvt Ltd.
12. Srivastava, R. & INSTITUTE FOR HUMAN DEVELOPMENT. (2020). Understanding Circular Migration in India: Its Nature and Dimensions, the Crisis under Lockdown and the Response of the State. In *IHD-CES WORKING PAPER SERIES (Report WP 04/2020)*. INSTITUTE FOR HUMAN DEVELOPMENT. http://www.ihdindia.org/Working%20Papers/2020/IHD-CES_WP_04_2020.pdf